

4

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1574 W. ROAD
LITTLETON, PENNSYLVANIA 18976

ANTHROPOLOGY
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02138

3/71

R 102 + R 101 ①

⑦

agreedly all rocks cannot pass
w/ N face. In fact goes to S + C of
many villages of Fung
+ 5 rods ~~at~~ South
photos planter + colour of
my good hand note village note

road to left ~~in~~ ~~direction~~ ~~of~~ ~~the~~ ~~road~~
west 5 rods north road

~~road~~ of burnt rocks - a group.

210 probably a little higher
+ other ~~rocks~~ } + C 7m
cuts level of rock on NW knoll
not unlike ~~knoll~~
lots of ~~rocks~~
found ~~at~~ ~~on~~ ~~the~~ ~~knoll~~
rock face v rough.

3/71

KUNAR TAKHTE

Toll Mill

(5)

BUREKI

beas 299

vain village beas Kunar Takhte a 39

by edge of plain fields all and unorganized
grain + loose masses of eroded rock

long depression beas 20° ~~long~~
cut out at N end

visible from road at ~~2 1/2~~ 3 m
across rd

sig. 113 + 219.. 3 small tells

to South. north fields

stone ground ploughed all way up
to just below summit

rain ht

3 humped

Tea house mid way from Takste
Northwards beside river.

3 jars

Made: Kazem

applied on below river ^{older river} newer
hot near before.

the next tea house north
trason.
either coil or slab

DALAKI

220° to village + c ~~1000~~ ³⁰⁰⁰ m from road

a real people cultivated next way of
+ ~~to the~~ hot c 8m.
sky while in middle of plain.

date 174.

89-121 top road.

c 1 km or 800 m ^{1 km} from village

K 180.

low that eroded area were unringed palm
trees reported from each other

E rd is ~~200m~~ ^{200m} from end of
road. where road separates to W of
rd to Tomboc.

over area of 350 MP's + 100 flat
me birds. walk round on W end is
35 feet NS + 20 feet EW
+ C 40 as ht.

to work at 100m on edge of irrigated land
+ have points P.

1050 + C 120 m from house.
clear within 40 m to within cloud
around it.

all rather late.

flat day area.

150 m LR to top of road from house
N part of 2 groups

then 150m LR all little stuff

in 300m +

248 - 75 / 300.

270

250.

270m N-S to road.

+250. to enclosure.

to west c 300m

another little road with lot
not collected as rose stuff

K181+2 ②

140 to home. c 340° to K180
real stuff mound

08-2

38-56

NS. 130m LR

EW. 180m LR

a real little road c 50m at not bad.
~~edges~~ in unarranged talus
+ c 200m from edge of talus

road to Tamboc runs to west.

K182. 100m to S + E on road in unarranged talus

v low c 28 x 30 x 15m

not much foliage 20c + got crop
thru way all of it

K183

90° to K182 + c 150m

80 m to SE ungrated land
c 30 cm ht + c 40 m sq.

1 km down road to the town of Charyngah
+ 200 m ~~to~~ East of road.

Charyngah c 1.5 hrs to the west the
is little more recent road c 30 feet + 20
~~ft~~ + 15 m ht.

308

$$\begin{array}{r} 283 \\ 2830 \\ \hline 2800 \end{array}$$

K184. Sans Wam etc.

on N ~~edge of~~ line edge + E edge of
line of gravel terraces on edge of
concreted. & cult of tobacco.

To N in open area with grass but no
palms street freshly planted along
low road

small white house on SF like other
Sans Wam sites

to N of rd Charyngah -

70 m sq rise c $\frac{1}{2}$ m
above gravel terrace above it

K 185 just above K184

E 25 m South.

gravel terrace 4m above plain

○

○

○ K184

on ridge marked by road.

like 184 for nests

1 km to SW

gravel terrace lies SW-NE

360 m x ~~100~~ 200 at SW end

1/2

186. gravel terrace, some grass

K187

gravel terrace on edge of Chelo
nests bear 172° to W end
of 186

+ closest part is c. 120 m at

gravel terrace is 3-4 m. (186 etc

is c. 5 m

long dimension rolling terrace
NE-SW // to other

range

length of gravel 350 CR

with width c 120 etc

little pottery. Bones abandoned
1971

not much of it in site

253^o telegraph

800m good palms

K188 to E of road: palms.
100m at EW + 60 NS
houses to NE.

water level:

road c 30 - 40 m -

only water before.

up Hakein rd. to it + 300 m from road
900 m from junction to where telegraph
houses 253^o

K189 bank land some non palm
trees flat area with herbs c 120m
NS + 80 m est

2 along river
establishes flat area on swampy bank

c 80^o + ~~to~~ 1.05 km

from zone bridge

K 190 on flatish with non palm
scrubs etc..

etc

small matter of flat area at road

c 250 x 70 m. est

+ est c 500 m beyond

road. 189

extension of long range of roads

from Mashwin

on bridge from where

road along river in the lower is
down c 400 m

on bearing bank

to crossing of

c 323^o

K191

well low site white shells on top
c 40 fms + 20

light Mussels.

+ 50 mht.

estimated 350-400 m bears c 80° from
K192

K192.

N-S 300 m + m. E-W

ht not 1 1/2 m

middle 275° to school at.

place opposite Dehn

Sed has 12 + set of mddda
+ S in ~~the~~ grass

600m + 210° to Dehn

white stones etc. uneven eroded, irregular
falsely? fms to E.

Low to North.

K193

153 to K192 + at 200 m.

173 Dehn

eroded fms on it fms ~~eroded~~
over an area of ~~800 m~~
no real height but great area mostly
+ irregularly rough.

rough area along side north of area c
1200 m on edge of irregular fms

K194

some shells on SF between 2 points

barrier land

E-W 50 m LR

N-S 120 m LR

leaving to middle of narrow site
1200

400 m from closest end of T. Dehn.
on bearing to Dehn of 170°

K195. on edge of irrigated
cultivation on left of rd from asphalt
to Balluk.

Cultivation to N
irrigated fields to E
doubt to W x S
irrigated slightly raised area
lots of pits + some stones

size:

N S - 200 m + 50 v little road

E W - 150 m + water flat 100 m

rice + red / lots of pit

- SW are rounders

K196 is 500m bear 135° ft 195
irrigated fields on it
just NE of M/B school building
c 60 m + ~~200~~ 40 east
eroded area sloping up to fields
lots near 200 x 200
corn school of Danda

To S of school making c 100 m
south over area of flat c 350 m by east.
late weeds

K197

on edge of cultivation bear 37°
to Dandan house school at 15 km.
flat grass weeds c 100 m x 80

c 500 further on edge of irrigated
cult. road 100 x 100

c 40 30 m rounded no water
to it of track

another late note on edge of wellhead
c 500 m further.

on rock part N of well case

c 50 faces N another v little
c 20 x 20.

valued brick + gatch + 1 lot
rough shell

+ on set 1500. front of high mound

k 198

late rough + later

concrete road due on South
fottery, eroding out of sand dunes
in area

clear shells

Sarmat perhaps 140°
c 100 m sq.
900 m from

c 800 m from N of line
of lakes

K 199 probably 2 buildings.
 1 building walls robbed out
 with thick b/c MP x STP.
 + 70 feet S and other things around.
 out of gravel terrace on N end
 of terrace

late rough ch.
 under base 10 feet to N.
 all on N end of gravel terrace

550 m W of road
 also west

on same line 100 m from road flat
 at approx 70 x 100
 modern Shaly late
 nothing collected

K 200
 80m x 180 CR
 SE-NW
 SW

flat some rubble. + 2 mounds
 each c 20 x 30 feet rising
 out of it
 almost all late
 rubble.

~~Sunderby 15. 50.~~
~~Anger 15. 50.~~
~~base.~~

BILLS

SITE

100 paces N S + 60 paces E W
to gate of road

on junction of 2 parallel roads
of Masari - see red markings
burial to which it bears 60°

not quite at right angles

stone wall alignment over whole
area of gravel

on N side eroded by river
cut into ~~gravel~~ stone alignments

level 5 is just rough diff (27)

+ leaves a diff) total 1 1/2 up

unquarried steps up to 6 blocks for
+ 2 + 1 1/2

make walls c 3 1/2 - 4
or a little less

rather water worn + muddy sand

max depth of walls + all c 1/2 m

c 10 m diff to river

the North across the river
is several canals + pools
+ palm trees.

+ NE palm trees around village

well formed vegetation

road 13 paces wide

(B) odd leads were not destroyed by bulldozers

Cam, opposite it photographed ledge
Mena by standing buildings etc. 1m
not v. d.

'rooms' on curves of India map
gravelled round enclosure

K179

100 m S of rd from Mina

leads 150° to Serendipity
school house 60° to Qaleh
is in N bank of perennial river
+ on top spur of mountain.

walls made of river pebbles
flatt.

↳ towers on A + none on +
wall signs + towers etc on photo
on note that rises c 100 ft
above river.

~~etc~~ c 60 ft x 60 ft
enclosure

H 17 - Dek Ali

Dek Ali

135 faces EW + 120 NS

abandoned towards west
not at 4 metres.

50
near to N + are c 100 m away on S

c 200 m

E of road near flood
cultivation all around
+ water.

v eroded soft surface
c 1.3 km or being c 135° from
Karin.

ARDEO

before

and birds supposed to have fed
by stone

water volume c 120 x 80

little, made wooden

porters got roof etc. to antiquity

135 faces EW location c 200 m E of

12 of NS

not at 4 m

eroded towards W

near led to North + another c 50 m away ES

~~200~~

visited 3/69 / AGW, WMS

9/71 " M EP

K 178.

c 300 m N of Kasim

flat fields some trees old irrigation
field lines crossed by tracks into
Kasim.

~~by road c 200 m to Kasim;~~

quite a lot of pottery

650 m x ~~200~~ 300

E-W

flat land some cultivation but a good
lot of pottery

K 177. bears 130° to Kasim.

+ track K178c 1.00 km.

+ size c 70 x 70 m

road runs c 1 m v eroded.

176

K ~~175~~ bears last site c 100 m to E
of road road bears 125° to Kasim

+ on S shore of stream by + on road.
mounds - some no cultivation + c
120 m sq. v cut up + use c 1 m
road.

road may bet near 177 + 176 another
little underfoot, 1 m into
c ~~50~~ 30 + 50 m.

K 201 scrubby area some mounds
up to 1 m with some debris

King - 150 x 70 est.

E-W N-S.

+ cut 150 m from. just c 400 m
from great bend.

bears 16° to Minik Qalik

+ 120 m from SW corner to K200
bears 260°

+ bears to K199 - 215°

202. less to 201 - ~~230~~ 20
200 - ~~230~~ 330
197 - 225

one wall is 201 + 200
foot low walls let seen.

2 low roads 20 paces up +
approx 180 + 100 of pottery
: number remaining
on level of road + c 200m away

203

immediate road runs $2\frac{1}{2}$ m on left
edge of gravel terrace to mt
~~the~~ ridge
39 m from road to East
mounds + gravel around
mound .40 paces up
+ Med water below it for
200 m not v dense
good + lots of Med on mound

204

Old Kukulcane location on ruins of
India - fort.

on long mesa c 300 m long
c 100 ft high
less 190°

on middle of mesa
stone ruins of 11 buildings maybe
we see 78 paces + 23

width less c 35 paces.
+ these near rises up.
low stone ruins.
also some stuff further down.
plate roughly c 100 paces
probably got part of calendar

205. Mts from bottom of
 mesa on K. side
 fallen stuff from top but also
 on base of T.

on eroded ground with rubble

Other side a steep hobble
 holding

1 face = 2 mm.

4 3 2
1 m = 992 | 77 | +5 | A1

165 325
250 355 38 A2

260 20 3 4
300 33 79 A3

1 face 7944 940 faces = 1880
∴ 1 face = 2 metres 2 mm

diff

1880
∴ 1 m = 782
∴ 1000 m = 782

310 - 50° base line

1 block of to ~~320~~

$\frac{7}{1} + \frac{380}{328}$ faces = 318 metres base li

+ face = ~~320~~ 154 ~~12~~ ~~12~~

15 1/4 m = 190 faces

7 7/8 m = 9 5/8 faces

3 8 1/2 m = 4 7 1/2 faces

19 1/4 m = 23 3/4 faces

ie 20 m = c 24 1/2 faces

~~380~~ 380 380
380 380
760 190
950 faces
940 faces = 782 m

782 m = 1880 cm.

~~380~~
 2.46753
 $154 \overline{) 380,0000}$
 308
 720
 616
 1040
 924
 1160
 1078
 820
 770
 500
 462
 38

1 m = 2.46753 mm

A | B
 ⑤ 325 | 359

312?
 ? ⑥ 312 $\frac{1}{2}$ | 355

⑦ 302 | 344

⑧ 295 | 339

⑨ 298 | 348

⑩ 281 $\frac{1}{2}$ | 329

⑪ 272 | 315

B ← 570 A-12人

①
 319 A 321 note terms ②
 20 B 10°
 wt both corners

③ ~~346 B~~
~~321 A~~
 50

323 A ④
 4 B ①

11 has real moved from it 310°

35/hrs

A B
259/292 / 12

12 wall looks like 16 faces

13 54/296

12 - 40 + 40/hrs
B A A
313/256 1/2

14

15 A B
267 348

16 272 102

16 winding

17 282 1/2 0 1
18 286 345

Then hard edge to 9

307. 356 19
lean 300°
sol rot C / 40/hrs

comes to 16 to (19)

A	B
271	14

55 nos
A B

257	11	(20)
-----	----	------

A	B	
247	19	(21)

52⁰ (22)

23
(242) road.

70
↓
Hole

A	B	
202	95	(23)

(24)	A	B
	183	- 99

(25)	A	B
	160	83

(26)	A	B
	136	73

(41)	A	B
	241	261

.15 face worked road

42

5

c 80m

185°

beam to RB

30 nos

160

54°

Creek 30 x 80 ft

Cover lens 249° to 2.

Lower along wall.

B from cover 270°
160 feet to internal rods
c80 feet thick

213° from 2 ed of 20 feet
wide base

B 207½ A 218 (43)
~~has~~ ~~been~~ ~~beds~~, are c 80-90
 m from wall

B 202 ↔ A 216 (44)

to E 20 + 30 + 30 + 20

(45?) B ○ + ○ 20x20 tch
 A 206 197

30/8
 2/23

227 to B. 36 + 39

Now B is more to forward
 built by then 127

41 ft $\times$ 180°

60 feet $\times$ round, round

66 feet on 53°

a 20 feet $\times$ round

200 ft

179

257 / 289

re 180 feet at 6R 208° = 28°

the 200 feet at 6R 223-4° = 43-4

= 162 meters at ~~28°~~ 28°

the 178 meters at $\boxed{43\frac{1}{2}^\circ}$ 223-4

138 / 72 (50)

165 / 84 (51)

(208)

58° to grad of hill slope

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \triangle 80 \\
 + 158 \\
 \hline
 = 238 \\
 = \textcircled{190m}
 \end{array}$$

24 + 2
 80 + 3
 98 1/2 + 4

31

21 x 2
 115 x 1

358^b - 120 hrs

37 1/2 tot 2
 74 tot 3
 c 115^b tot 1

32

210^b - 72 hrs

33

43 2
 92 1/2 3
 154 1

for (34)

line of holes runs 140°

length LR 180m

width ≈ 5 fms

52 + 2

155 + 1

104 + 3

(34)

210 x 1

322 x 2

(35)

all over area. inches + gatch.
about base rose trees of wall dia - stone

(57)

7 x 4 embedded
with red/white

$220^\circ + 35$ fms to cliff

~~18 x 1
328 + 2
85 + 3~~

(36)

10 x 5 rolled out when
stone flatter found

4 151
3 181
2 ca 211

14

rock 171 - 3
142 1/2 - 4

from Schreiner Dugan etc down + lands
mish tray 25 faces by
ble + white long white frog
oc . one .
not kept

205

tray 25 x 20 faces by road from
South road to N abern

c 200 m back to M5 millage of 206
no fossils collected 'Nawband
K way / late bog / late P
ble + white / oc / rt orzle mi
mis

+ c 100 m + 600 collection
dry ground it water led to South
12 on it + gabrielle

K207.

low gravelly road runs along ~~cultivated~~
flood cultivated fields.

beam 40° to Gnarlandy
c 15 hrs. across fields
size c 70×40 m.
ht c 5m

K208 from Narraon Gargi

road curves SSE c 10 hrs or 9-8 hrs
= Litch on lee side
c 100×50 very few reeds
indeed.

(61)

K209 within it + around it
v + w shot leaf.

EW - 60 m
NS - 40 m

ht 75 cm.

c 5 hrs ^{up rd} from St Hovir large
+ c ~~300 m~~ ^{100 m} to west of
river - road. ht village from
Narra Gargi is c ~~250~~ ³⁰⁰ m
an bearing 1000

K210

another late site north ~~and~~ west of
around

450 alt
 240° + c ~~500~~ m from. size village
roads up to 120 ht

NS - 80 m EW 60 m

c 100 m from
put before it hits river bed.

across road + to E of rd c 100
 on with to NE culminated under
 continuous flat + rose north of to (a)

flat water ~~at~~ ~~est~~ ~~at~~
 200 m up
 rare ~~at~~ ~~est~~ as 209.

up ~~branch~~ to side of river marked on ²¹¹
 my map, India Map. fort is 19c

Wall of 1713 exposed with stone

river entrance has summit.

total c 300 x 150 m
 over is eroded grand conglomerate

stone boulders
 rose boulders north ~~to~~ covered
 lanes. 2 wells wide.

210^A below the boulder hill top
 marked up side valley.

all late.

2 spots at line

watch 211 top
 210 also

0-98 / 226 +

250.

290

155 m

late compact C + D = c 300 x 150

K 211

not bright 590m + 330m

Very eroded ground + bottom of A c 100m to E of river

cut by roads a lot of pottery all through spec - B where some brick ruins + 12 in middle.

long dimension 47°

$$A = 170 + c 220 \text{ d constant of rd } c 120$$

$$B = 170 + 330$$

$$C = 150 + 150 \text{ rather } c 250$$

$$D = 100 + 100$$

river slope W - distance follows all around

river flood catchment all around

K 212. late rd site 100 x 80
 W across river + to N of rd from K 211
 c 100 m from river bank + village to W
 Wt has per stone?

pieces to N + W Those to west looking
 feet dead

520	360
420	460
135	520
385	520
420	170
460	
420	

~~K 213~~ 5.20

a mound c 5 m ht

c 60 x 100 m stony or rubble
the top c 2 m ht.

late stone age etc.

stone houses and

burns from end of collection of Uchuhun

286 = 478

152°

new notes R 120 in Hradková
3 collected in Summer ~~1970~~ 1970

Qaleh Sang numbers

Inner line ? = S2A

outer enclosure select stands S2B
or outer area

KS. side.

also labelled KS Kerman, S2C

Q Sang Survey
roads by side

S2D

Plan of Shards - Insultide

Small crates	Small	SM	Small	Small	Small	Small crates
MD	K	M	SE _{SE}	PTD	SE	big crates
MD 397	K	MD	SE	PTD	SE	big crates
MD 391	K	K	SE	SE	SE	big crates
S MD	WATRU	MT	SE	SE	SE	big crates
QAM	K	K	SE	SE	SE	big crates
S	SH	K	SE	K	SE	big crates
M	CHAM	K	SE	K	SE	big crates
	KAQ					big crates

M, or MD = Man Dacht

M + = N of Lake Batslegon

K = wood fars + Keran

SE = Senta

QAN - QAN - i - Ah Nahr

PTD = wanted to go to England

~~RT 291~~

~~R1 - R6~~

~~350 or 352~~

Location R4.

to R1 45°

to R6 15°

to R27 179°

to water T 127 $\frac{1}{2}$ °

to Ten House 112

Location of R6.

R1 from 350 - 352°

R4 from 15°

R7 253° from R6

R9 128° to R6

R10 156° to R6

R12 176° to R6?

R21 32° " R6

R23 35° " R6